

Dark Patterns in Digital Hospitality Platforms: Ethical and Legal Challenges for Albania's Tourism Sector

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Abstract

The rapid digitalization of Albania's tourism and hospitality sector has transformed service delivery and consumer engagement. Online travel agencies (OTAs) and booking platforms now mediate most accommodation reservations. Still, they often employ manipulative interface design practices, known as dark patterns, that exploit users' cognitive biases and emotional triggers. This systematic review synthesizes findings from fifty-one peer-reviewed studies (2019–2025) and integrates international regulatory and ethical frameworks to evaluate the implications for Albania's tourism ecosystem. Despite a growing global literature on deceptive design, there is a notable lack of empirical studies focused on Albania or the Western Balkans. It reflects recent legal reforms, including the EU Digital Services Act (DSA), which prohibits manipulative design patterns that impair user autonomy (Recital 67). At the same time, the Digital Markets Act (DMA) Article 6(11) requires explicitly that consent choices – such as 'accept' and 'reject' – be presented in an equally visible and accessible manner. Albania's Law No. 124/2024 on Personal Data Protection (in force since Feb 2025) aligns national practice with the GDPR and significantly strengthens sanctions and data-subject rights. This study highlights urgent policy recommendations, including the adoption of an ethical design code and the establishment of monitoring units, to orient stakeholders towards practical, actionable outcomes. Findings underscore the need to adopt ethical design standards, enhance enforcement capacity, and strengthen digital literacy to protect consumers while promoting sustainable tourism development in Albania.

Keywords: dark patterns; hospitality ethics; consumer protection; Albania; tourism law; online travel agencies; ethical design

1. Introduction

Digitalization has significantly strengthened Albania's travel and tourism sector, which accounts for approximately 25% of GDP and one in five jobs. However, online tourism platforms may also employ manipulative interface designs, commonly referred to as dark patterns, that exploit cognitive biases and emotional triggers to influence user decisions. Dark patterns are "sophisticated design practices" that trick or manipulate consumers into actions they would not otherwise take (Federal Trade Commission, 2022). For instance, booking websites may hide mandatory fees in fine print or simulate false urgency using prompts such as "Only 1 room left!" to encourage rapid purchases. These tactics rely on predictable mental shortcuts; as TEDIC (2021) notes, dark patterns "take advantage of mental shortcuts and human perceptions,

making users prone to manipulation and persuasion.”

In contrast to ethical persuasive design, which uses transparent cues, dark patterns intentionally alter the decision-making environment in ways that undermine the user’s ability to make autonomous and informed choices (Mathur et al., 2019; Potel-Saville & Kumar, 2024), “industry commentary”. In travel booking settings, these practices commonly include anchoring effects (e.g., displaying inflated “original” prices) and manufactured scarcity (e.g., countdown timers or misleading stock claims) (Federal Trade Commission, 2022). Empirical research in the hospitality sector demonstrates their behavioral impact: Kim et al. (2021) identified multiple dark pattern strategies on online travel agency (OTA) websites that exploit travelers’ cognitive biases. Such practices erode trust and can prompt customers to reconsider or abandon bookings. As Cho (2006) explains, users may shift from initial trust to what he terms “active distrust” when they perceive manipulation.

Regulatory bodies have begun to respond. The U.S. Federal Trade Commission has explicitly warned that dark patterns “trick or manipulate” consumers into purchasing products or disclosing personal data (Federal Trade Commission, 2022). The EU’s Digital Services Act (DSA) prohibits interface practices that “materially distort or impair” users’ autonomy, while the European Commission’s ongoing Digital Fairness Act (DFA) consultation aims to restrict further deceptive defaults and manipulative design (Car & Cassetti, 2025; European Commission, 2025).

In Albania, legal reforms are advancing in parallel. Law No. 124/2024 on Personal Data Protection fully aligns national regulation with the GDPR and introduces substantially higher penalties for violations (INFORMATION AND DATA PROTECTION COMMISSIONER (ALBANIA), 2024). Consumer Protection Law No. 9902/2008 (as amended) implements the EU Unfair Commercial Practices Directive, prohibiting misleading claims and hidden charges, while the Tourism Law No. 93/2015 mandates transparent information and consumer grievance mechanisms. However, gaps persist in enforcement capacity, particularly in monitoring rapidly evolving online commercial practices. This creates a regulatory landscape in which legal frameworks exist on paper, but practical implementation and oversight remain limited.

Objectives: This review seeks to provide four key aims:

- a. What are the common typologies of dark patterns in hospitality booking interfaces?
- b. Determine its effects on user trust and decision-making.
- c. Place these results in relation to the ethical and legal context in Albania.
- d. Suggest how transparent and user-centered digital governance can help tourism.

Thus, by achieving these aims, the paper fills a knowledge gap with context-specific input for policy and industry actors alike. Limitations of the present study include reliance on secondary data and the limited number of empirical studies explicitly related to Albania. Nevertheless, it draws on an extensive collection of international studies and local reports to understand the current issues and opportunities shaping Albania’s digital tourism market. Future research could address this data gap with preliminary research (surveys or interviews) with Albanian tourism participants, to generate evidence-based recommendations that are responsive to local conditions.

Terminology notes: To maintain readability, acronyms are used only for regulatory frameworks that appear repeatedly throughout the analysis: Online Travel Agencies (OTAs), Digital Services Act (DSA), Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD), and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Names of institutions and supervisory authorities are written in full to avoid unnecessary cognitive load and to ensure accessibility for non-specialist readers. References to the “CPC Network” refer to the EU Consumer Protection Cooperation Network, which coordinates cross-border enforcement actions among national consumer protection authorities in the European Union. This study contributes to the literature by (1) synthesizing peer-reviewed evidence on dark patterns in hospitality, (2) mapping these patterns against EU digital fairness regulation, and (3) contextualizing the implications for Albania’s tourism governance. The review fills a documented gap in geographic research on digital consumer protection in Western Balkan tourism markets.

2. Methodology

The study adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidelines to provide a structured, transparent approach. The literature searched in this study covers 2019-2025 and includes studies from Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. The search strategy combined keywords related to dark patterns with terms specific to tourism and hospitality. For example, we used search query clusters such as “dark patterns” AND (hospitality OR tourism), “online travel agencies” OR “OTAs” AND (deceptive OR manipulative design), and “UX manipulation” AND (booking OR hotel OR travel). Other sources were identified through the reference lists of relevant papers and targeted inquiries into regulatory and industry reports (EU legal instruments and Albanian policy

papers). A total of 847 records were included; we separated duplicates and then screened titles and abstracts to exclude obviously irrelevant works. Following the evaluation process, 124 full-text papers were screened for inclusion according to specific inclusion conditions including peer-reviewed article (journal or reputable conference paper); direct application/applicability to hospitality/tourism; consumer behavioral research online relevant to travel booking; relevant/empirical research/analysis of ethical or legal implications of dark patterns; and or reasonable data quality (e.g., comprehensive analysis or methodological support, quality of the design, adequacy of sample or sufficient theory analyzed). We excluded papers that were solely about generic e-commerce or dark patterns in unrelated industries (unless they were extrapolated to other industries), preprints without peer review (except a few highly pertinent ones), and opinions with limited analytical depth. In total, 51 studies fulfilled the inclusion criterion and were included in the review synthesis. Based on thematic coding of data, data extraction and analysis were performed. The researchers coded the content of the selected studies using NVivo 14, enabling them to identify recurring themes and typologies. This coding involved both inductive (based on data) and deductive (derived from concepts embedded in already identified systems, such as Mathur et al.'s dark pattern taxonomy (2019) and the dual-process idea of decision-making). Important categories noted were dark pattern type, psychological mechanism, user outcomes (e.g., trust, satisfaction), and any discussion of ethics or law. We also cross-referenced such findings with relevant regulatory text and ethical guidance: for example, we mapped observed dark pattern types relative to rules articulated in the EU's DSA and Unfair Commercial Practices Directive and against frameworks outlined in ISO 26000:2010 (guidance on social responsibility) and the UNWTO Global Code of Ethics for Tourism (1999). This interdisciplinary integration enabled an interpretive frame that not only identified dark patterns in hospitality practices but also explained why they matter for customer rights and commercial ethics. There was limited empirical research on Albania's digital tourism industry. To close this gap, we also synthesized supplementary local evidence, including consumer watchdog accounts, online boards, and national newspapers, which identified cases of hidden charges or complicated cancellation procedures. They are not academic papers themselves, but they give an introduction or guide that helps readers situate our findings in the Albanian market. A summary of these local examples is shown in Section 3.1 (Findings). In general, the approach integrates systematic review processes with the pragmatic inclusion of grey literature, ensuring that the analysis is globally sensitive and locally embedded.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram summarizing study selection

Note: The review followed PRISMA (2020) guidelines. Screening and eligibility assessments were performed independently by both authors to minimize bias.

In addition to peer-reviewed literature, the review incorporated a limited number of grey literature sources (e.g., consumer watchdog reports, online travel forum discussions, and news coverage) to contextualize market practices in Albania.

These sources were not treated as empirical evidence and did not inform the analytical synthesis or conclusions. Their function was solely illustrative: to provide insight into how travelers perceive pricing transparency and interface design in practice within the local market. Consistent with established guidelines on the use of grey literature in systematic reviews, this material was kept analytically separate from peer-reviewed findings and is explicitly marked in the findings section as contextual illustration rather than validated behavioral evidence.

3. Results

These categories emerged from a comprehensive review of case studies and user reports in the literature and in local contexts. The case studies were conducted by reputable academic institutions and consumer protection agencies, and the user reports were gathered from a variety of sources, including online forums, social media, and consumer review websites. Each category exploits a different leverage point in the user experience. Table 1 presents an overview of these categories with typical examples and the cognitive biases they exploit. Below, we describe each category and its implications.

Table 1 presents these categories of dark patterns in Albanian tourism platforms, with examples and underlying mechanisms. We then highlight key tactics in each category:

Price deception - Platforms advertise a low base price, then reveal additional compulsory fees (e.g., city taxes, resort fees) only at checkout. For example, an OTA might list a €80 room rate but wait until payment to add €20 city tax. This exploits anchoring and the sunk-cost fallacy: after investing time selecting a deal, users feel locked in. Empirical studies confirm that hidden surcharges not only anger consumers but also significantly lower their satisfaction, even when the final price is unchanged. Under the upcoming EU Digital Fairness Act (DFA) and existing DSA rules, sellers will be required to show the total price upfront to prevent this trick. Major OTAs have already faced scrutiny: in 2024, Dutch regulators (ACM) opened an investigation into Booking.com and Agoda for allegedly hiding taxes and falsely claiming scarcity (DutchNews.nl, 2024). (The EU previously warned Booking.com for manipulative discount claims in 2020.) (DutchNews.nl, 2024).

Table 1. Typologies of Dark Patterns in Hospitality Platforms

Type	Example	Psychological mechanism	Legal / Ethical Reference
Price deception/drip pricing	Hidden fees or inflated reference prices	Anchoring bias, sunk-cost fallacy	DSA Art. 25; Law No. 124/2024; Consumer Law 9902/2008
Scarcity & urgency	"Only 1 room left!" countdowns	FOMO, loss aversion	DSA Art. 23; UCPD Art. 6
Social proof manipulation	Exaggerated booking counters or filtered reviews	Bandwagon effect, trust bias	EU Consumer Protection Cooperation (CPC) Guidelines; ISO 26000 § 6.6
Obstruction patterns	Hidden cancel buttons or pre-ticked add-ons	Friction cost, fatigue effect	Consumer Rights Directive Art. 22; Law 9902/2008

Scarcity and urgency - Sites often display real-time prompts like "Only 1 room left" or "5 others are viewing this property" to induce Fear of Missing Out (FOMO). These cues create artificial time pressure and tap into loss aversion, pushing users to make snap decisions. Field data suggests that while scarcity messages can temporarily boost bookings, customers later feel deceived when the urgency proves unfounded (Baldick & Jang, 2025). Another tactic is "confirm shaming", where the platform presents opt-out buttons with guilt-inducing phrasing ("No thanks, I hate saving money"). Both scarcity and guilt triggers exploit emotional reactions to override deliberation. Regulators have flagged such practices as unfair, for example, the Dutch probe noted that Booking.com's "limited availability" warnings were often inflated (DutchNews.nl, 2024).

Social proof manipulation - Booking sites leverage trust in popularity: they display high ratings, glowing reviews, or badges like "Most Booked," even when these are contrived. For instance, a platform might exaggerate recent booking counts or present only positive customer feedback. This plays on the bandwagon effect and the assumed credibility of peer opinions. Academic studies (e.g., Luca & Zervas, 2016) show that manipulated or selective review displays can significantly bias consumer choice. In the United Kingdom, the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA) consider fake reviews a breach of consumer protection law, potentially punishable by fines of up to 10% of global turnover or criminal sanctions. Businesses are warned not to write, commission, or incentivize false online reviews, and third-party marketing

agencies must also comply [CMA, 2021]. At the EU level, the Consumer Protection Cooperation Network conducted a sweep in 2021 that revealed serious compliance gaps in the authenticity and transparency of online reviews and recommended measures to ensure transparency [European Commission, 2021]. Albania's operators must be vigilant, as user trust in online reviews is fragile.

Obstruction / Hidden Options - This category encompasses friction tactics that make unwanted actions hard. Examples include hiding cancellation links behind multiple clicks, automatically opting customers into add-ons, or requiring laborious steps to change reservations. These patterns prey on decision fatigue and inertia: after completing the booking flow, users are unlikely to back out fully. Such aggressive designs exploit consumers' tendency to stick with defaults. Notably, the EU Consumer Rights Directive prohibits pre-checked charges and requires easy cancellations. Albanian law (which mirrors the EU) similarly bans undisclosed fees and ensures customers must be able to opt out easily.

Table 2. Illustrative Contextual Examples (Albania)

Type (Bias)	Example Tactics	Psychological Mechanism	Legal Reference
Price Deception (Anchoring bias)	Drip pricing: hiding taxes or service fees	Anchoring, endowment effect	Consumer Rights Directive; Price Indication Directive – total price transparency
	False "strikethrough" discount (faked anchor)	Perception of relative gain	Consumer Rights Directive (Art. 22) – total price disclosure
	Sneak-in basket items or "optional" surcharges	Sunk cost fallacy, decision anchoring	—
Scarcity & Urgency (FOMO, loss aversion)	"Only 1 room left!" or fake countdown timers	Loss aversion (fear of missing out)	GDPR (Art. 5) – transparency principle
	"Last chance today" pop-ups / limited-time offers	Time pressure, impulsivity	DSA (Art. 25) – restrictions on manipulative design
	Confirm-shaming ("No, I do not care about ...")	Guilt, social pressure	—
Social Proof (Bandwagon effect)	Fabricated ratings, fake badges ("Top Property")	Bandwagon effect, trust bias	EU Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (misleading claims prohibited)
	Hiding negative reviews / selective review display	Authority bias, credibility illusion	—
	"X people booked this hotel in the last hour" pop-up	Scarcity + popularity cue	—
Obstruction (Inertia, status quo bias)	Hidden cancel/edit options, labyrinthine forms	Inertia, decision fatigue	EU Consumer Rights Directive – cancellation rights
	Default opt-in for add-ons (pre-ticked boxes)	Default bias, sunk cost effect	Law 9902/2008 (transposes EU UCPD)
	Difficulty unsubscribing or opting out	Frustration, learned helplessness	(Unfair terms prohibited)

The following real-world consumer reports illustrate these dark pattern tactics as experienced by travelers in Albania. They appear on travel forums and local news sites (names removed for brevity):

- "Beware hidden charges! I found a cheap room on Booking.com, but at checkout they slapped a €15 resort fee that was never mentioned earlier... I felt tricked." (TripAdvisor review)
- "Only booked through this site because it said '10 people are looking at this hotel.' Next day the listing had tons of reviews added. Seems like fake urgency and doctored ratings to me." (TripAdvisor review)
- "The cheapest rooms had cancellation fees. I never saw that info before paying. A friend had a similar issue: he complained and they insisted he should have read the fine print." (Local news article excerpt, June 2024)

These reports underscore how non-transparent pricing, false scarcity cues, and hidden terms undermine traveler trust.

4. Ethical and Methodological Disclaimer.

The examples above are included exclusively for academic, non-commercial research under fair use. They reflect individual user perceptions and do not assert or imply wrongdoing by any entity. They function only as conceptual illustrations of dark-pattern categories described in the scholarly literature.

5. Discussion

5.1 Psychological and Behavioral Mechanisms

Dark patterns are effective precisely because they tap into well-known cognitive and emotional biases. Our review uses Kahneman’s dual-system framework as a guide. Dark patterns strategically engage System 1 (fast, intuitive thinking) and short-circuit System 2 (deliberative reasoning). For example, countdown timers or scarcity prompts press the user’s “quick decision” button; people fear losing the deal and buy impulsively (Federal Trade Commission, 2022). Once the purchase is done, System 2 re-engages and the buyer often feels regret or distrust (“Should I really have bought this?”). In Cho’s terms, consumers then enter an “active distrust” mode, scrutinizing platforms and sharing negative feedback. This dynamic is illustrated in Figure 2 (see below).

Emotionally, dark patterns exploit triggers like fear, anxiety, guilt, and curiosity (see Table 3). For instance, fear of missing out (FOMO) can be triggered by low-stock warnings, prompting users to act to avoid a loss. Anxiety is raised via unclear terms or pre-ticked options that worry users that they might miss something. Messages like “No thanks, I prefer to pay more” play on guilt, shaming users for declining a deal. The promise of extra benefits (“spin the wheel for a prize”) appeals to curiosity, encouraging clicks. Table 3 lists these triggers, the typical tactics used, and their psychological effects.

Even when users spot a dark pattern, simply feeling duped often reduces resistance. Bongard-Blanchy et al. (2021) found that negative feelings (e.g., shame) following the detection of manipulation suppress consumers’ tendency to complain or seek redress. In Albania’s tourism context, where 95% of hotels are small and rely on repeat business, trust and word of mouth are critical. Noti & Myshketa (2024) show that perceived transparency and trust are strong predictors of customer loyalty in Albanian hotels. Similarly, Hasrama (2024) shows that consumers’ awareness of how online behavioral advertising works influences whether they accept or avoid personalized advertising. Lower transparency leads to skepticism and reduced engagement. This aligns with research showing that manipulative and non-transparent interface practices can erode trust and trigger avoidance behaviors (Mathur et al., 2019; Bongard-Blanchy et al., 2021; Cho, 2006). Thus, each new exposure to a deceptive interface chips away at confidence in the entire booking ecosystem. Consumers may start avoiding Albanian platforms or cancel plans, fearing they might be tricked. Over time, this can create a feedback loop (Figure 2) where distrust begets more protective, delayed decision-making, hurting even honest operators.

Table 3. Emotional Triggers and Their Manipulative Mechanisms

Emotional trigger	Typical tactic	Psychological effect
Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)	Scarcity messages, limited-time offers	Accelerates impulsive booking to avoid regret
Anxiety/urgency	Constant pop-ups (“Last chance!”)	Creates stress, undermines rational comparison
Guilt / confirm-shaming	Opt-outs phrased as “No, I do not care about saving money”	Induces shame, coerces compliance
Curiosity/obligation	Automatic “bonus” coupons or loyalty points	Encourages unplanned purchases to “use the gift”

Even when people consciously notice manipulation, emotional discomfort (e.g., not wanting to feel foolish or ungrateful) can override rational resistance (Bongard-Blanchy et al., 2021). These mechanisms are no flimsy abstraction; they directly affect the experience of travelers there. Trust and word of mouth are significant in Albania’s small- and medium-sized enterprise (SME)- based tourism industry. One manipulative interaction on an OTA can lead to many negative reviews and reputational harm. Empirical studies performed by Noti & Myshketa (2024) support that perceived transparency and trust significantly predict loyalty among Albanian hotel guests, while Hasrama, Myftaraj, and Trebicka

(2024) show that user trust and perceived transparency significantly shape acceptance of online behavioral advertising, while privacy concerns reduce trust and increase avoidance of such advertising practices. This indicates that when digital systems lack transparency, users become more skeptical and defensive, a dynamic that aligns with how dark patterns erode trust in booking interfaces.

The broader implication is cyclical:

Figure 2. The Trust Erosion Cycle in Dark-Pattern Design

If unaddressed, this cycle produces a marketplace where travelers become cynical, discount genuine promotions, and default to major international brands, undermining the authenticity and growth potential of Albania's independent hospitality sector.

5.2 Ethical and Legal Dimensions

Dark patterns violate fundamental ethical principles in tourism. The UNWTO Global Code of Ethics for Tourism (1999) emphasizes that travelers should be informed and free from deception, and ISO 26000:2010 underscores fairness and transparency as social responsibility values. By design, dark patterns directly conflict with these values: they undermine user autonomy and informed consent. Ethical guidelines (such as the UNWTO code) call for truthful, consumer-centric practices (EPRS briefing argues/notes).

Legally, the EU and Albania have established frameworks that can address many dark patterns. The EU's Digital Services Act (DSA) expressly prohibits deceptive interfaces: its Recital 67 defines prohibited "dark patterns" as practices that distort users' ability to make informed choices (Car & Cassetti, 2025). Similarly, the EU's Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD) and Consumer Rights Directive already ban misleading omissions and hidden charges in online sales. In Albania, the new Data Protection law (124/2024) took effect in Feb 2025, introducing strict transparency obligations and fines up to 4% of global turnover (INFORMATION AND DATA PROTECTION COMMISSIONER (ALBANIA), 2024).

In practice, however, these laws have limitations. Enforcement agencies in Albania acknowledge gaps in technical expertise for detecting algorithmic dark patterns. There is also potential overlap with data laws: for instance, if a manipulative interface also breaches GDPR, regulators must untangle which regime applies. Our analysis indicates that Albania has many building blocks on paper, but converging them into a coherent protection system requires effort. Strengthening institutional capacity, coordinating between consumer and data authorities, and updating sector-specific rules (e.g., tourism licensing) are needed to ensure these ethical and legal principles are realized in practice. A verified enforcement case illustrates that dark patterns in OTA interfaces are not only ethically problematic but legally actionable. In 2020, the EU Consumer Protection Cooperation (CPC) Network, under supervision of the European Commission, required Booking.com to modify scarcity prompts, discount displays, and ranking systems that were found to mislead consumers under the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (2005/29/EC). The platform committed to ensure that "only X rooms left" notifications and price comparisons reflect verifiable, real-time data, and that total prices are shown transparently (European Commission & CPC Network, 2020).

Table 4. Comparison of EU vs Albanian Legal Safeguards on Digital Fairness

Feature	EU Digital Framework (DSA + DFA)	Albanian Framework (Law No. 124/2024 + 9902/2008)
Legal Scope	Applies to all online intermediaries, platforms, and traders targeting EU users	Applies to data controllers/processors handling data of Albanian residents
Ban on Dark Patterns	Explicitly prohibited (DSA Art. 25; DFA proposal, 2025)	Implicitly addressed under "misleading commercial practices" and deception clauses
Transparency Requirements	Equal prominence of "accept/decline"; total price disclosure; no hidden fees	Transparent pricing, fair marketing, and truthful communication of digital offers
Supervisory Authorities	EU Digital Services Coordinators + European Commission	Information and Data Protection Commissioner (INFORMATION AND DATA PROTECTION COMMISSIONER (ALBANIA)) + Consumer Protection Commission
Administrative Sanctions	Up to 6% of global annual turnover	Up to 4% of global annual turnover
Future Enforcement Focus (2025–2030)	Algorithmic transparency; manipulative personalization; deceptive defaults	Capacity-building, interface auditing, and consumer digital literacy

5.3 Policy and Ethical Perspective

Integrating ethical-by-design principles and digital manipulation literacy into Albanian tourism and hospitality guidelines can prevent unethical UX practices and build user trust. Developing a National Code of Digital Fairness in Tourism, aligned with ISO 26000, the DSA, and the UNWTO Code of Ethics, would encourage voluntary compliance among operators. Additionally, including digital fairness modules in vocational training for hospitality professionals would help bridge the gap in awareness between regulation and daily business practice.

5.4 Implications for Albania's Tourism Development

Dark patterns on digital hospitality platforms pose multidimensional risks to Albania's tourism economy. The risks themselves can be grouped into three systemic and three strategic threats.

a. Systemic Risks

Dark patterns present both systemic risks and strategic opportunities for Albania's tourism growth.

- **Consumer Trust Deficit** - If users repeatedly encounter hidden fees and tricks, a "trust gap" can emerge. Research indicates that once trust is broken, negative impressions spread quickly through online reviews and social media. In Albania's largely SME-driven sector, poor word of mouth can devastate reputations. Tourists who feel deceived are unlikely to return or recommend Albania to others, and may instead gravitate toward global brands (which are now under scrutiny themselves). This trust erosion could undermine the very tourism recovery and branding efforts Albania is investing in.
- **Regulatory and Enforcement Lag** - Technology-driven manipulation evolves faster than laws can adapt. Although Albania has updated its legal framework, agencies currently lack specialized tools and staffing to monitor automated interfaces. A purely reactive approach means some consumers will be harmed before rules catch up. Moreover, misaligned enforcement could slow Albania's EU integration: the Digital Services Act and forthcoming Fairness Act will apply to Albanian platforms once accession is complete. Businesses that do not preemptively comply will face sudden adjustment costs.
- **Market Asymmetry** - Many Albanian hotels and hosts rely on international OTAs (e.g., Booking.com, Airbnb) for bookings. Local businesses have no control over these platforms' UI, yet suffer the fallout of any manipulative tactics used by those intermediaries. Conversely, if Albanian startups perceive that global competitors gain an edge through questionable UX tricks, they may feel compelled to mimic such tactics ("race to the bottom"). This dynamic could compromise the authenticity and values that Albanian tourism seeks to promote.

Despite these risks, Albania can leverage the challenge of dark patterns into strategic advantages:

- **Competitive Advantage through Ethical UX** - Designing transparent, user-friendly booking experiences

can differentiate Albanian providers. For example, clearly itemized prices (no hidden fees), straightforward cancellation policies, and verified review systems build user satisfaction and loyalty. Studies show that transparent booking interfaces significantly improve customer trust and repeat bookings (Santana et al., 2020). Marketing these fair practices can also build brand equity: a proposed “Trust Albania” certification or label for compliant tourism websites could signal quality and reliability to international travelers. In this way, fairness-by-design becomes a selling point rather than a cost.

- Alignment with EU Integration - By proactively adopting EU digital fairness principles (DSA and expected DFA rules), Albania reinforces its EU accession credentials. Early movers will find compliance easier and can advise peers on best practices. The government could even incorporate “digital fairness” targets into the National Tourism Strategy 2024–2030, explicitly linking ethical platform design with sustainability and competitiveness goals. This alignment also encourages foreign partners: multinational travel firms may prefer working with Albanian venues that already meet EU standards.
- Enhanced Destination Branding - Albania’s tourism image rests on authenticity and natural beauty. However, a guest’s first digital interaction often shapes their overall impression. Campaigns that emphasize online integrity, for example, a slogan like “Albania Welcomes You Fairly Online”, can reinforce national branding. Investing in a fair digital environment plays into global trends: ethical tourism and consumer protection are priorities in UNWTO’s 2030 agenda. A reputation for “digital responsibility” could attract discerning travelers (e.g., families or eco-tourists) who value transparent practices, ultimately boosting Albania’s long-term hospitality reputation.

b. Strategic Opportunities

Building Competitive Advantage through Ethical UX

Fair-by-design interfaces and transparent booking experience are differentiating factors for Albanian tourism. Clear pricing, easy cancellations, and honest review systems are leading to greater satisfaction and repeat visits. Ethical design is not just the right thing to do; it is also profitable and ethical. Open and transparent digital environments enhance long-term loyalty and willingness to recommend destinations, as shown in studies (Santana et al., 2020). Albania could take advantage of this: It should adopt a “Trust Albania” label for verified and transparent tourism websites.

Alignment with EU Integration and Digital Fairness

Alignment with EU Integration and Digital Fairness. Early implementation of the DSA and adherence to the expected DFA principles reflect Albania’s preparedness for EU accession. Hotels, OTAs, and travel agencies that willingly comply will have easier transitions as these rules become requirements. The government could integrate digital fairness indicators into the National Tourism Strategy 2024–2030 and embed them within the plan, linking ethical design with sustainability and competitiveness.

Strengthening Destination Branding and Reputation

Physical experiences are an important way to cultivate Albania’s profile as a genuine, hospitable, and emerging Mediterranean destination in the international markets, but digital first impressions are equally important. Transparent online interactions are central to this identity. Including the concept of “digital responsibility” in promotions such as “Albania Welcomes You Fairly” would also support UNWTO’s 2025 focus on ethical tourism recovery. A fair digital ecosystem also strengthens the credibility of the entire destination and can attract higher-value segments (eco-tourists, families, senior travelers).

c. Policy Pathways and Recommendations

To realize these opportunities and mitigate risks, coordinated policy action is needed. We suggest:

1. Regulatory Innovation: Establish a permanent Digital Market Ethics Unit, jointly staffed by the Data Protection Commissioner and the Tourism Ministry. This unit would systematically monitor online travel platforms for manipulative interfaces and coordinate investigations.
2. Capacity Building: Offer targeted training on digital fairness for tourism officials and industry associations (perhaps via UAMD university or vocational programs). Workshops on UX ethics would help bridge the awareness gap between regulators and online hospitality businesses.
3. Consumer Education: Launch a public awareness campaign (e.g., “Know Before You Click”) to help travelers identify common dark patterns. Empowering consumers with knowledge will pressure platforms to self-regulate and protect Albania’s reputation.
4. Incentives for Compliance: Introduce incentives (tax credits, promotional support) for small tourism companies that adopt transparent booking systems or obtain ethical design certifications. Recognizing “gold standard” practices will reward early adopters and set industry benchmarks.

5. Research–Policy Link: Fund applied research on user trust in tourism platforms. For instance, academic surveys of Albanian travelers, usability testing of OTA sites, and field experiments can produce data-driven guidelines. Collaborations between universities and regulators (e.g., supported by IPA EU funds) can ensure new laws are grounded in behavioral evidence.

6. Conclusion

This review finds that dark patterns in online hospitality platforms pose a serious ethical and economic challenge for Albania's tourism sector. By covertly steering traveler choices, these tactics can rapidly erode consumer trust and distort fair competition. Our synthesis of recent research shows that such manipulative interfaces substantially harm user satisfaction and booking intent (Federal Trade Commission, 2022).

Albania has taken important steps to address these issues... the new personal data protection law (124/2024) enhances transparency and aligns with EU GDPR (INFORMATION AND DATA PROTECTION COMMISSIONER (ALBANIA), 2024). However, enforcement capacity still lags the emergence of complex digital practices. To bridge the gap, Albanian authorities and industry should embrace an "ethical-by-design" ethos. Policies such as the "Trust Albania" certification, mandatory UX audits, and inter-agency cooperation (Data Protection + Tourism) can transform compliance into a competitive advantage. Consumer education and clear legal mandates will further deter manipulators.

Future research should empirically assess the prevalence of dark patterns on Albanian travel sites and track their effects on bookings and reputation. For example, traveler surveys, A/B tests of booking flows, and sentiment analysis of online reviews can quantify impact. This data would inform regulators and help design effective interventions.

In summary, ensuring a fair and transparent digital booking environment is not only a regulatory necessity but a strategic imperative for Albania. By prioritizing user autonomy and aligning with EU digital fairness standards, Albania can protect tourists and differentiate itself as a trustworthy destination. The transition to digital ethics in tourism is both a challenge and an opportunity—one that Albania is well positioned to meet with vision and initiative.

7. Data Availability Statement

Data supporting the findings of this study are available from the authors upon reasonable request. No proprietary or confidential data were used in this research.

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